

homothallism to heterothallism and then to the infertile state in which the sexual function might have been lost.

Southern Yunnan Province is a center of rice origin and has a long history of upland rice cultivation. The possibility that parasitic differentiation could be established from grasses to cultivated

rice (H. Kato's hypotheses) might have occurred in this area. The *Pyricularia* in this area exhibit the same properties as those of grass isolates (*E. indica*, *E. coracana*). Many isolates produced a lot of perithecia and produced sterile perithecia in single culture (see table). The formation rate of *Pyricularia*

becomes gradually less from south to north—from temperate to cool to cold regions—until it cannot form. The trend from high to low fertility corresponds with direction of the spread of rice cultivation. ■

Reaction of some rice germplasm to leaf blast (BI) in Guyana

C. R. Paul, National Agricultural Research Institute, Mon Repos, East Coast Demerara; and J. S. Nanda, Guy/86/002, Guyana

Blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* is an important rice disease in Guyana. We screened 377 breeding lines for leaf BI resistance during Aug and Sep 1991. Breeding lines were grown in International Rice Blast Nurseries to score leaf BI reactions. Highly BI-susceptible variety Rustic was used as susceptible check and in spreader rows. Varieties Diwani and 6039 served as resistant checks.

Entries were inoculated at the four-leaf stage with chopped infected leaves. Nursery beds were irrigated twice a day between 1000 and 1100 h, and 1500 and 1600 h. Beds were covered with polyethylene sheets at night to maintain high humidity.

Reaction of rice breeding lines to blast (BI) in Guyana, 1991.

Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin	Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin
CT8008-3-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR54791-19-2-3	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-5P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56382-123-3-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-6P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56383-46-1-2-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-7P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56446-94-3-1-2	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -1-3-2	3	MR	Guyana
CT8222-4-1-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -2-3-1	3	MR	Guyana
CT8238-6-14-P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR9 F ₂ -1-3-2	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-1-3P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR12 F ₂ -1-2-3	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR126 F ₂ -2-1-1	3	MR	Guyana
Diwani	3	MR		NAR126 F ₄ -2-5-2	5	MS	Guyana
Surinam				NAR151 F ₄ -4-3	5	MS	Guyana
Eloni	3	MR		NAR210-1-1-4	1	R	Guyana
Surinam				NAR210-1-4	1	R	Guyana
IR8192-31-2-1-2	3	MR	IRRI	NAR218-2-4-4	3	MR	Guyana
IR44624-127-1-2-2-3	3	MR	IRRI	Pedigree 9	3	MR	Guyana
IR47761-27-1-36	1	R	IRRI	Pedigree 12	3	MR	Guyana
IR51678-93-2-2	5	MS	IRRI	TX06	5	MS	USA
IR52350-93-2-2	3	MR	IRRI	TX49 (Aromatic Lemont)	3	MR	USA
IR53306-36-1-3-1	1	R	IRRI	6039	3	MR	Guyana
IR53306-64-1-3-2	3	MR	IRRI				
IR53649-AC5-2	1	R	IRRI				

^aScored (0-9) using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and MS = moderately susceptible.

Entries were scored on a scale of 0-9 using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when the susceptible check had scored 7-9. Sixteen lines were resistant,

16 lines moderately resistant, and 6 lines moderately susceptible under conditions conducive to severe disease development (see table). ■

Resistance of BPH-resistant rice varieties to *S. furcifera* in the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST).^a

Variety	Genes for resistance to BPH	Plant damage rating ^b	
		SSST	MSST
IR47-B2-6	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
Mudgo	<i>Bph1</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 a
Ptb18	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Gambada Samba	<i>bph4</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Babawee	<i>bph4</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
ARC10550	<i>bph5</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 b
Swamalata	<i>bph6</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
Ptb21	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Ptb33	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
IR26	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
IR36	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR56	<i>Bph3</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR62	<i>Bph3</i>	2.2 b	1.0 b
IR64	<i>Bph1</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
TN1	No gene	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT; av of 5 replications.

^bDamage was rated on a 0-9 scale where 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately resistant, and 7-9 = susceptible.

Pest resistance— insects

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper (*Sogatella furcifera*) in rice varieties with different genes for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

R. Velusamy, M. Ganeshkumar, Y. S. Johnson Thangaraj Edward, and M. Gopalan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

We evaluated 15 BPH-resistant rice varieties for resistance to *S. furcifera* using the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST). The experiment was laid out

in a split-plot design with screening methods as the main plot and varieties as subplots. Treatments were replicated five times.

In the SSST, seeds of BPH-resistant varieties and susceptible check TN1 were sown in rows in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm). At 7 d after sowing (DAS), seedlings were thinned to 15/row and infested with eight 2d-instar *S. furcifera* nymphs/plant. When all TN1 seedlings were dead, plants were rated for damage on a 0-9 scale where 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately

resistant, and 7-9 = susceptible.

In the MSST, seeds were sown and seedlings thinned as described for the SSST experiment. Plants were infested with four 2d-instar nymphs/plant at 20 DAS. Damage was rated at 25 d after infestation when TN1 was dead.

In the SSST, insects in the initial infestation killed TN1; in the MSST, the progeny of the infesting insects killed TN1.

There were distinct differences among BPH-resistant varieties in both tests (see

table). Mudgo and IR64 (*Bph 1* gene), Rathu Heenati and IR62 (*Bph 3* gene), Gambada Samba and Babawee (*bph 4* gene), ARC10550 (*bph 5* gene), Swarnalata (*bph 6* gene), and Ptb21 and Ptb33 (*bph 2 + Bph 3* genes) were rated as resistant in both tests. Varieties Ptb18 and IR36 (*bph 2* gene) and IR56 (*Bph 3* gene) were susceptible in the SSST as seedlings, but were highly resistant as the older plants in MSST (see table). ■

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

(*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée) and stem borer (SB) (*Sesamia inferens* Walker)

S. Ray, M. Singh, and G. Singh, Indian Council for Agricultural Research Complex for Northeastern Hill (NEH) Region, Sikkim Centre, Tadong, Gangtok 737102, India

LF and SB can be destructive rice pests in Sikkim. Infestations of LF and SB occur from late Aug through Oct. We observed peak infestation of LF at panicle initiation, the last week of Sep. Yield losses to both pests can be avoided by using resistant varieties.

Twenty-four cultivars with medium to late maturity from around India, including the NEH Region, were transplanted in 2-m² field plots during 1990 and 1991

kharif (monsoon) seasons with three replicates. All recommended crop management practices were followed except plant protection measures. For each entry, we recorded number of hills with LF and SB infestations at panicle initiation and total hills per plot.

Sikre, Khonorullo, Khusaro, RCPL 3-5, and Dhanse were found moderately resistant to LF, 13 cultivars were moderately susceptible, and 6 cultivars were susceptible. Sikre, Srinivasa, IRAT141, Sarassa, and RCPL3-4 were moderately resistant to SB, 15 cultivars were moderately susceptible, and 4 cultivars were susceptible (see table). ■

Screening of rice cultivars for resistance to LF and SB. Sikkim, India, 1990 and 1991 kharif seasons.

Cultivar	LF incidence (% infested hills/plot)			Reaction ^a	SB incidence (% infested hills/plot)			Reaction
	1990	1991	Mean		1990	1991	Mean	
VL 23	23.1	8.3	15.7	S	6.4	3.3	4.9	MS
Nagoba	8.6	9.5	9.0	MS	2.5	2.2	2.4	MS
Sikre	0.0	4.5	2.3	MR	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Srinivasa	7.3	10.6	8.9	MS	0.0	3.6	1.8	MR
Zhapara	7.0	10.8	8.9	MS	1.2	4.2	3.3	MS
DR92	11.3	13.6	12.5	S	2.6	12.8	7.7	MS
Khonorullo	0.0	3.1	1.5	MR	7.4	1.6	4.5	MS
TRUA 490	0.0	11.2	5.5	MS	14.1	2.1	8.1	S
IC25697	5.9	2.2	4.1	MS	10.3	7.8	9.0	S
Khusaro	2.0	0.8	1.4	MR	0.0	4.4	2.2	MS
PP2-24-1557	12.3	5.5	8.9	MS	7.0	1.3	4.2	MS
RCPL 3-5	3.2	5.5	4.3	MR	9.5	2.0	5.8	MS
IRAT141	8.0	8.2	8.1	MS	2.3	0.7	1.5	MR
IR36	10.0	5.7	7.9	MS	12.9	14.9	13.9	S
Sarassa	11.3	6.9	9.1	MS	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Jaya	16.7	13.3	14.8	S	2.9	9.9	6.4	MS
ICPL 131	4.1	7.6	5.8	MS	3.1	1.5	2.3	MS
Akhanpan	11.1	6.3	8.7	MS	17.5	11.5	14.5	S
ARU3	13.3	7.8	10.6	S	1.1	6.6	3.8	MS
CSR80	17.1	7.8	12.5	S	2.3	3.5	2.9	MS
Attey	4.8	8.2	7.0	MS	1.2	3.4	2.3	MS
Vikash	10.9	4.5	7.7	MS	4.4	3.5	3.9	MS
RCPL 3-4	9.9	9.1	9.5	S	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Dhanse	0.0	3.7	1.9	MR	7.2	6.8	7.0	MS

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, and S = susceptible.

Evaluation of rice genotypes for resistance to orange-headed leafhopper (OHLH) in the Hill Zone of Karnataka, India

V. V. Belavadi, B. Mallik, A. Manjunath, and Y. G. Shadakshari, Regional Research Station (RRS), Mudigere 577132, India

Orange-headed leafhopper (*Thaia subrufa* M., Cicadellidae: Homoptera) is a serious pest of summer rice in the Hill Zone of Karnataka. Feeding by nymphs and adults causes leaves to become speckled. The speckles coalesce when infestation is severe, leading to hopperburn symptoms. Grain losses can range from 30 to 70%.

Rice genotypes were screened for resistance to OHLH in two phases at RRS. We mass-screened 243 varieties in phase one (1986-88). Each entry was planted in three rows with two replica-